

I.FAST

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Business Development Case Report

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ABSTRACT

The task 3.2 in Work Package 3, "Industry Engagement", aims to optimize the industrial innovation and knowledge transfer potential of I.FAST R&D activities. This report summarizes the approach and exemplary results from analysing the I.FAST Internal Innovation Fund (IIF) projects with respect to their business case potential. Together with a case framework suited to these projects, prior information was connected with results from surveys and interviews to form a starting point for an evolving business case, which can be refined through continuous engagement with the projects, industry partners and stakeholders.

I.FAST Consortium, 2024

For more information on IFAST, its partners and contributors please see <https://ifast-project.eu/>

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	Name	Partner	Date
Authored by	D. Safi	DESY	13.05.2024
Reviewed by	M. Vretenar [on behalf of Steering Committee]	CERN	21.05.2024
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1 Introduction

As indicated in the I.FAST project proposal, the task 3.2 of work package 3, "Industry Engagement", is interested in understanding the industrial innovation and knowledge transfer potential with regards to I.FAST R&D activities.

I.FAST projects are striving to achieve their R&D goals, strongly motivated by their scientific interests and requirements. In addition, often overlooked, there is a significant potential to

- facilitate **transfer of knowledge to industry**, and
- **stimulate the build-up of added industrial value** in terms of creating new IP, creating new market opportunities for existing companies, facilitating the creation of spin-offs, etc.

One of the goals of the task is therefore to support the I.FAST beneficiaries in achieving an optimal exploitation of this potential. For this purpose, the analysis of the status of the activities concerning both risks and opportunities for industrial innovation and technology or knowledge transfer can help supporting the realization of the activity's potentials. This was done through surveys executed within the work package.

Following this assessment, the task 3.2 is working on ways to further support the I.FAST beneficiaries in this respect. Thus, it was planned to identify activities that can profit from a closer investigation of this potential and support with a plan to pursue it. The activities funded by the I.FAST Internal Innovation Fund (IIF) fall well within this general scope and were therefore deemed ideal for this investigation: the funded projects identify and address innovative solutions in accelerator technologies with a viable commercial/industrial potential. Many aspects in this direction have already been part of the selection process¹. A business case shall support the further development of a commercialization plan, as part of the project.

This report summarizes the approach and exemplary results from a preliminary analysis towards a business case. In principle, the results only serve as a first starting point for an extensive business case for the activities, which themselves would be living documents developed alongside the ongoing technological developments in the project. Thus, this document here only briefly touches on a variety of relevant topics, while they are in more detail discussed together with industrial partners and the target fields. Moreover, this report shall outline not only the approach but some recommendations along with first outcomes.

¹ See I.FAST Deliverable Report 4.1 on "Evaluation criteria for IFF projects and Evaluation Body", <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7612543>

2 Chosen Approach for Business Development Case Investigations

There is a variety of projects within the I.FAST project, that are well suited to be studied for developing a business development case in this task. This is especially the case with the projects funded by I.FAST via the IIF. These in fact represent an optimal application domain for the goals of task 3.2, due to the requirements the proposals had to satisfy:

- Consortium: at least one I.FAST beneficiary and one industry.
- Initial TRL 3 or higher (from proof-of-concept to laboratory/environment validation).
- Project contributes to improving sustainability of particle accelerator technologies.
- Project must have potential for industrialization or commercialization.
- Project must have potential to attract more resources than what is deployed by IFAST alone.

Therefore, it was decided, that a selection of projects from the IIF to support their progress and develop general measures based on a concrete example is most efficient to directly support the goals of WP3.2. The developed approach consists of multiple steps:

1. Development of a business case content framework, consisting of all relevant aspects for the business development case, as well as a corresponding fact sheet summarizing all (prior) given information from the IIF proposals in all categories relevant for the business case development.
2. Researching additional initial information (public sources, ...) to fill possible information gaps in the framework, as far as possible.
3. Gain additional insights into all the projects through a KT/TT and Innovation Potential survey (carried out through WP3.1), with questions, e.g., on the technology maturity and possible support available from a KT/TT office.
4. Definition of a set of relevant criteria for selecting cases useful as examples, consisting of the suitability of the business problem and value proposition, the foreseeable impact (economic, social, environmental), the potential of the project and commercialization, the clearness of the applications within or apart from the direct scope of the task, and the significance of the addressed markets.
5. Develop questionnaire for in-depth interviews with the selected projects, addressing the range of categories considered in content framework.
6. Generate information from given data and interaction with group, possibly additional tools (e.g., patent and research databases).
7. Consider relevant strategies and recommendations, suggesting the adoption of general measures and instruments, and check whether the activities have sufficient (ongoing) support

within their home institutions (i.e., the KT/TT offices) for activities aimed at developing towards the potentials identified in the business case.

3 Business Case Framework

All business cases for the considered projects should contain all appropriate information for the relevant internal or external stakeholders, e.g., partners or decision makers for the business case. Such information categories might vary significantly considering the type of activity, the commercialization approach, the IP situation, the motivation of the research groups, as well as the overall technological maturity and application readiness. In the following, a rough framework of aspects relevant in connection to the IIF projects is outlined, that could be discussed with the IIF projects to support them in developing their own business cases.

- **Business problem description or opportunity statement:** The R&D activity must address a clear and well-defined problem or opportunity. Thus, a clear and concise idea and formulation of the actual problem at hand or addressed opportunity without too much emphasis on the presented solution is a crucial first step for the business case. The business problem description should set the ground for the solution presented in the next step and be of high enough relevance for the applications outlined later. Usually, this part should be tailored to the target audience of the business case, e.g., to make sure they understand the problem and share the need for a solution.
- **Proposed solution or value proposition and applications:** Based on the problem description / opportunity statement, an adequate solution is derived, which is the core of the R&D activity. The proposed solution usually includes detailed descriptions of the proposed project or initiative, including the scope, objectives, and deliverables. This is not necessary in the case of the here outlined business case framework for the activities in I.FAST, as we are only interested in the innovation potential itself as a first step, with implementation considerations being in the hands of the projects and their home institutions.
- **Technical challenges, description of the technical agenda:** Developing and commercializing new technologies in the field of the IIF / I.FAST projects of course always involves overcoming technical challenges, such as ensuring or increasing stability and reliability, validation, or transition from prototype to industrial scale and production standards. Projects may need to invest in additional research and development to address these maturity issues. Thus, a description of remaining technical challenges within the frame of the commercialization approach with the identified technical steps needs to be included as part of the business case.
- **Analysis of efforts and benefits, funding and costs:** A rough examination of the expected efforts and benefits of the proposed project or initiative supports assessing the proposed solution, including both quantitative and qualitative information, as far as possible. Bringing new technologies to market can be expensive, and projects may need to secure funding from further investors or partners to support the efforts, with the analysis of efforts being important information therefor.

- **Market research / landscape, market acceptance:** Containing an investigation of the potential market situation and landscape supporting the business case, giving indication of the relevance and potential of the solution, although especially this aspect is in most cases not addressed within the I.FAST / IIF projects yet, being relevant in the more later stages. Especially the topic of market acceptance is of high relevance, as it can be difficult to convince potential customers to adopt a new technology, especially if it requires them to change their existing processes or behaviors or fields with a high level of regulation are targeted. This is especially relevant, if the business problem is not severe enough or the provided value of the solution is too little. Also, the projects or responsible commercialization partners may need to invest in regulatory activities, marketing or partnering efforts to help build awareness and understanding of the technology.
- **Competition or alternative solutions:** New technologies often face competition from established players and technologies in the market, who may have more resources and a better standing, as well as other academic research groups. Many activities are in early stages, where it is not necessarily fully clear, which alternative solution among the competitive approaches will in the end be most commercially viable. Projects may need to differentiate the technology by highlighting its unique benefits or advantages. Especially in the field of accelerators, many technologies are initially more complex than necessary or desired in the targeted industrial applications settings.
- **Risks and regulatory obstacles:** An assessment of the potential risks towards market efforts and other parts within the business case is usually a quite crucial part of the investigation. A detailed consideration of the risks associated with the proposed project or initiative, and an according plan for the mitigation (or at least management) of these risks increase the viability and potential of the case. In the case of the I.FAST / IIF projects, the associated and identified risks are initially more on the technical side, due to their technological level and the technical emphasis of the groups, but in later stages further more market-related risks are to be considered. Also, bringing new technologies towards application often involves considering complex regulatory environments, strongly intertwined with the topic of market acceptance. This is especially relevant in safety or medical applications, which are a typical target for technologies from the field of accelerators. Understanding the relevant/necessary approvals and certifications (if already existing) and obtaining them can severely delay or hinder commercialization, invoking significant cost and effort. This also increases the risk associated to the business case.

The following investigation/analysis will not in all cases adequately address all these aspects. Instead, it will provide a starting point, from which further investigations can be initiated, and provide a first overview of the corresponding case. Thus, it aims at understanding the strengths and weaknesses of the business case to see where additional supportive action from the project or the I.FAST work package might be beneficial.

4 Interview Questionnaire for Business Case

As part of the investigation, and as described in Chapter 2, a questionnaire for in-depth interviews with activities was developed, that can be used as a guideline for the discussions and the development of the business case, addressing the range of categories considered in the content framework. Based on these questions, the prior information can be extended by additional information from the project group. Not all questions are relevant for all projects, as some projects might not address commercialization themselves but through partners, that would take care of certain relevant aspects, e.g. marketing strategies and product cost calculations.

Business Problem and Opportunity

1. Can you describe the technology and its potential applications in layman's terms?
2. What issue or opportunity is the business case addressing?
3. What is the background and context of the problem or opportunity?
4. What unique value does the project offer to customers or stakeholders?
5. What are the key benefits or advantages of this technology over existing solutions?

Applications, Alternative Solutions and Market

6. Who do you see as the primary users or customers for this technology?
7. Are there any existing solutions that address the same problem or need as this technology?
How does your technology compare?
8. Have you already received any feedback from potential customers or industry partners?
9. What is the size and growth potential of the target market?
10. Who are the competitors, and what is the competitive landscape?

Challenges and Risks, Timeline

11. What potential risks and challenges might the project face?
12. How will you mitigate or address these risks?
13. Are there any potential challenges or limitations to using this technology in a (the proposed) commercial setting?
14. What is the current stage of development for this technology? How much more work is needed before it can be commercialized? (compare to questions on TRL in KT-Survey)
15. Is time a sensitive topic w.r.t alternative solutions/competitors?
16. What is the estimated timeline for bringing this technology to market?

Costs

17. What are the initial and ongoing costs associated with continuing the project after IIF, towards further development or commercialization?
18. What would contribute to the cost of the product or application to the client/...?
19. Are there any hidden or unforeseen costs to consider?

Marketing and Communication

20. How would the project be marketed and promoted to target customers? What is a reasonable strategy for acquiring customers or clients?
21. Are there important external stakeholders (e.g., relevant partners, suppliers, ...) and how would you need to communicate with them and involve them throughout the project?

Further Steps

22. Are there any regulatory or legal considerations that need to be considered when bringing this technology to market?
23. Are there any potential partnerships or collaborations that could help accelerate the development or commercialization of this technology?
24. What steps after I.FAST are needed to continue developing this technology?
25. Do you already have follow-up plans? How are you continuing after the IIF?
26. Is this activity already discussed with the KT/TT office of your home facility? How is the contact/their support? Is the current level of support sufficient?

5 Analysis of the Potential in the IIF Projects

As outlined in Chapter 2, summarizing all available information provided by the IIF projects, a fact sheet was developed and filled out for them. Following the definition and assessment of relevant criteria for selecting a suitable case example, an interview was carried out with one of the projects that emerged as one of the most suitable, and the outcome is outlined below. Following the extended fact-sheet for this first project, for the seven other IIF projects short summaries of the fact sheets (without information from in-depth interviews) are outlined. For most projects, information through the survey on KTT and Innovation Potential could be included as far as available.

Example Case: “A Field Emission Cathode for a Travelling-Wave RF gun for High Brightness beams in Industrial and Small Research Facility Settings”

This specific case by a research group from the Paul Scherrer Institute addresses a new gun setup that is especially attractive due to its simplicity (meaning it is not too complex for, e.g., industrial settings) as a high-energy and high-brightness source of electrons. For this reason, it would not only be relevant to the accelerator community itself, but to a range of other applications outside the scientific domain. The business case shall support the further development of a commercialization plan within the project. Therefore, the business case primarily addresses a subset of the topics discussed in the Chapters 2 and 3.

Opportunity statement

Electron sources play a vital role in a range of applications both in industry and academia. The generation of electrons can be achieved through different emission principles. The most widely employed sources used in various industrial contexts are the so-called thermionic guns, i.e., heat-based release and provision of electrons with high enough energy for passing the potential barrier. While sufficient for many relevant medical and scientific use cases, these guns in principle inherently can only provide rather low brightness (and to some extent beam quality) due to the large thermal emittance from the cathode and the source size. Brightness is dependent on the beam size, the length of the beam, the divergence of the generated electrons and the energy spread. Ideally, divergence and beam are as small as possible to result in a bright beam. The lacking brightness in thermionic guns reduces their feasibility for some applications, e.g., specific medical applications where such beam characteristics are crucial, as well as high-energy electron microscopy or diffraction applications.

In the accelerator community, where such higher brightness electrons are required, so-called radio-frequency photo-guns are utilized. They require a driving laser for the photoelectric effect, through which the electrons are generated. The lasers required are of high peak powers, resulting in a very complex system, requiring engineers on-site during operation, and both the maintenance and the resolution of possible issues requires a high level of expertise of the involved staff. Thus, these requirements render them too complex and too expensive for many industrial settings, but also for smaller-scale research environments, e.g., university departments.

A third emission type is so-called field emission. These are already well-used in commercially available devices, e.g., electron microscopes, but an MeV source based on field emission, with high brightness (orders of magnitudes higher than both thermionic and photo-guns) and sufficient

simplicity, as would be required for a range of applications, is yet to be developed. Field emission type sources are far more unstable, as the electron generation is based on large electric fields on the surfaces. Increasing the electric fields to the required high levels can be problematic, as it can lead to the destruction of the field emitter and materials, too. Thus, while this type of source has a high potential for many applications in terms of the beam characteristics, current stability, maturity and complexity issues yet prevent their wide-spread use.

Value proposition

Within this project, a main goal is the development of a versatile, high-brightness MeV electron source based on a field-emission cathode that fits the gap outlined in the description of the business problem. As described above, field emission cathodes are already used in lower energy ranges, for instance in electron microscopy and diffraction settings. The main selling-point of the source proposed here is its integrated simplicity, opening up a range of applications, e.g., in medical settings, smaller-scale research institutes, or industry.

The proposed technological solution presents a new take on the gun, answering many questions and obstacles currently preventing more wide-spread use. The considered activity will answer the question, whether it can be used in an RF gun, testing what is achievable from a field emission tip from an RF gun. Today's TEMs and SEMs are based on such field emission sources, with high brightness but small currents. Typically, breakdown mechanisms (which are not fully understood) limit this type of source. They depend on the RF frequency: a higher frequency reduces the number of breakdowns that occur, which means that a damage of the field emission tip is less likely. Additionally, this allows for very short pulses, helping with longitudinal brightness. With an RF pulsed beam, high brightness as well as charge per area are possible, resulting in a good brightness source.

With any source where the pulse length is not controlled there is the issue that the RF field is inducing an energy spread, reducing the overall brightness. With the traveling wave structure, it is additionally possible to reduce the energy spread through phase manipulation. This is possible as the system is broadband in contrast to a standing wave system.

A strong selling point of the solution is that everything is done within one compact device with broad range of beam parameters. The beam energy, quality and brightness can easily be adapted to the required application, leading to a high level of versatility. As a result, with its simplicity and multi-purpose potential, it can be very interesting to a wide range of applications from medical, industrial, and academic fields, supported by a relatively low cost. The possibility to combine high brightness with both high or low currents can lead to a variety of use cases.

The considered activity will further narrow the gap to the high-energy application by prototyping, validation and test, as well as market considerations and plans for commercialization and exploitation.

Alternative Solutions

The issues with the other types of emission are already discussed earlier, as they constitute the relevant business opportunity. A more detailed comparison / analysis of the differences between them should be conducted within the project. In short, alternative solutions are:

RF photo-gun: significantly higher cost and complexity due to required components, such as lasers, at least one modulator, high-voltage and bunching systems, accelerator, etc., as well as staff- and expertise requirements in operation.

Thermionic guns: low complexity and inherently more stable, but lacking brightness for many applications.

There are other international research groups also developing RF guns based on field-emission, but mainly for the sake of e.g. fundamental material sciences research; anyhow, these solutions would not be in direct competition due to the different beam qualities.

Alternative solutions with similarly low complexity e.g. with thermionic emission could be found in integrating the cathode in the accelerating structure. Some research groups are working on this, but are in very early stage, addressing the field of medical applications. A detailed comparison between these solutions should be considered.

Applications

The discussed RF gun will broaden the possibilities for several techniques that are only available in larger institutes such as MeV electron microscopy and diffraction. These techniques are not possible with thermionic sources, as they do not reach the required brightness. They are interesting fields that are growing quickly and could become heavily used research areas, as for instance keV ultrafast electron diffraction is already well used with field emission sources already in use and a transition to MeVs would be the next logical step to approach also larger/thicker samples, especially with the possibility of low currents. While this is plausible, there are no good industrial sources available yet. In contrast, going for high current makes this also interesting for medical applications, e.g., FLASH therapy devices trying to be developed, or in general serving as a high-brightness source for a diverse array of medical applications.

Another interesting application is the area of electron irradiation, e.g., at higher energy of 10MeV, well suited for semiconductor irradiation. Using the source as a high-energy electron source for testing of semiconductors, to see how well they last under radiation and to study for instance the harshness of such a beam to components for space can serve as a viable alternative to today's approach using longer (10s of meters) accelerators. Also, security applications are feasible, requiring high energy electron sources, which also cannot be achieved well through thermionic sources with the same parameters. With the knowledge and interest of possible industrial partners that may want to be involved, a range of other applications can also be investigated.

In addition to these medical and industrial applications, there are also opportunities on the academic side, by enabling universities to provide compact and economically feasible accelerators to their departments, giving their students the possibility to make use of such beams while keeping costs under control. This is often not yet possible, as the electron source's laser is usually too expensive in

terms of invest, maintenance and operation. Likewise, it is anticipated that such an RF gun could be deployed in further small-scale research institutes, for similar reasons.

Starting Points for Business Plan and Commercialization Approach

As to the project, there will be a review of the IPR situation (to clarify the question, whether the intellectual property for this RF gun is owned by the facility) and there is the aim of extending these rights to include the already involved industrial partner and especially a yet-to-be-found OEM from the investigation. This OEM (or possibly further parties) should perform a market potential analysis, possibly started through the already involved industrial partners, which will help the commercialization approach. The current industrial partner together with the research facility can approach other suitable businesses to become the possible OEM of the product under development already in the current state of technological maturity (which is around TRL 2). Such early involvement of industry ensures a focus on aspects relevant for successful commercialization, such as manufacturability and cost-effectiveness. Together with the research facility, the industrial partner (and possibly OEM) can jointly translate the proof of concept into a tangible product meeting market requirement, based on the selected target applications.

A reasonable approach for commercialization as pursued by the group is to address this through the aforementioned OEM, that first needs to be found. The commercialization approach could be developed along the following actions:

- Partnership selection, potential OEM shall bring product/device to market.
- IP sharing agreements between facility, OEM and further partners.
- Market study through selected OEM/industry partner, as well as selection of applications, strategy development and last steps in product development (reducing cost, increasing reliability and usability).
- Collaboration with the Swiss “Park Innovare”, which aims to interface between research institute and industry for the sake of industrialization of accelerator technology.

The current project partners are possibly interested in the project and production of the device, but now not prioritizing the search for potential application fields and customers to commercialize the product themselves. A challenge is additionally to find a company that can fulfill the tolerances required in manufacturing for the accelerator components. The gun is more complicated to produce than thermionic sources. Splitting the manufacturing and addressing the market into two companies could thus ease the commercialization. The cost of the whole system together is difficult to assess as it depends on power requirements and further development steps, but could lie below the millions range for certain scenarios. Regarding the transition from a prototype level production to a more industrial production, the group is relatively confident, as there is prior experience at PSI within the context of the SwissFEL, which can be translated to this product. Still, as much is done through ultra-precision manufacturing, the production is not simple and it is not yet to be seen how well the cells can be manufactured in “mass” production.

Obstacles & Risk Analysis

Stability is a large risk that needs to be determined with respect to its severity. This is a significant inherent drawback of this technology, even in applications where field emission is already used in industry. The potential industrial success will rely on the level of stability the application can accept. This could be especially relevant and difficult in the medical sector. Still, at lower currents, it is assumed that the risk should be reduced significantly, due to the lower fields and currents. Thus, the challenges are less severe for e.g. electron diffraction and microscopy applications. The rest of the required parameters is in principle quite clear and low in risk – it is well-established, that they can produce extremely high brightness beams, even if it is not fully clear how long the beam quality can be kept up. Nevertheless, there are several aspects on the technical side, that need to be tested, although in terms of the RF-related technology there is good prior experience and control of the parameters.

Field emission cathodes might at the beginning demand more maintenance initially. Further development efforts could be necessary to enhance the device's reliability and ease of maintenance, and determine, e.g., optimal materials for the cathodes and best operational practices.

Also, not all industrial target markets might possess staff proficient in operation of such devices (incl. safety requirements in high-power RF, radiation shielding, regulation ...). Expert staff, training and safety infrastructure, as well as the general technical infrastructure drive the investment cost as a severe obstacle, although less severe than in laser driven alternatives.

Regulatory aspects pose another risk, depending on the application. This risk is considered manageable, as there is a lot of experience at PSI in medical applications, that can be translated to this activity.

Foreseeable impact and expected innovation

According to the project participants themselves, the R&D activity is primarily aimed at applications for science, but industry involvement and associated knowledge transfer can bring significant innovation to industrial products. The overall impact strongly depends on the results of the market study executed by e.g. an industrial partner, and the conclusions with respect to the potential within the identified selected target applications.

Maturity level and timescale

This activity is currently between “TRL 2 - Technology concept formulated” and “TRL 3 - Experimental proof of concept” and expected to reach “TRL 4 - Experimental verification in the laboratory”. For the technology itself (field emission gun), a proof of concept was already done by another research group. Thus, it is known that the concept can work. The given TRL increase requires the strong support and drive of a company with the intent of taking the technology and commercializing it. Then, the field emission TW gun could be market-ready in around 5 years (project team's estimate). The estimated time is subject to the industry partner establishing a suitable test facility for the device. Time is not a crucial factor for this technology for the group.

Additional recommendations and supportive actions

- Stronger industrial involvement is seen as beneficial, as well as the inclusion of additional partners with complementary expertise. It would help to involve another company with expertise in ultra-precision machining.
- The IP situation should be clarified, as was noted by the project group. Questions on how IP is regulated within the project, and what the I.FAST / IIF conditions are, are not fully clear and should be further clarified with the projects. The project states that it has good contacts with its own KT/TT office, which can provide sufficient support and help to resolve the outstanding issues.
- Support to develop a business plan has not yet been discussed with their KT/TT office, but it would be beneficial, as the researchers are yet more focused and experienced in the technical aspects of the development.
- The project group states that they are not yet experienced in how to propose such potential new products to industry and convince them to participate and collaborate, especially when the commercial potential is not yet fully clarified. They consider surveys and cold-calls not to be very effective. It is suggested, that either the industrial partner uses their network to support the business relations side of the commercialization plan, or the home facility (e.g. the KT/TT office or the innovation park). Starting the conversation with additional industrial contacts will support investigating additional fields of application and bring in relevant feedback for the business plan.
- Shared studentships/internships between the research groups and industry can represent a great opportunity to share knowledge while also funding further R&D projects.
- Questions about market size and growth potential should be answered in later business case considerations; these aspects are not clear at this stage. The industrial partners should be involved here.
- It would be beneficial to analyse the required efforts for further developments after the IIF project, e.g. how expensive (in terms of effort) it would be to bring the technology to the market.
- Competitive technologies might have advantages and disadvantages in certain applications, that should be further investigated.

6 Conclusion

This report provides an initial examination and first insights for developing a comprehensive business case related to the IIF projects. It outlines the preliminary analysis approach, presents initial findings, and proposes early recommendations for one example case, that will guide further detailed discussions with the group. Additionally, this document serves both as a blueprint for the approach and a platform for launching more in-depth explorations as the technological aspects of the project evolve. The discussions have indicated that the projects might benefit from further support in terms of assessing and developing the commercial potential of their R&D activities, to arrive at a more extensive business case and plan. This corresponds well with the findings from the KTT report developed in WP3.2, where such support was also requested. Some recommendations formulated for the example case can be extended to all IIF projects, such as the involvement of a KT/TT office, a further clarification of the IP situation as well as investigations into competitive and alternative solutions. There is a good opportunity to support the R&D activities further from WP3.2 to address these and further points to achieve an optimal exploitation of their knowledge transfer potential.